

Role Models for Educational Sciences and Educational Administration

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To cite this article: Collaborate, Current Science, Volume 5, No. 5-7, 2023, p. 239 – 259. - 0099-0001-2307-0510.

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ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

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Abstract

For many scientists, there is a lot of discussion about their experiences with students and colleagues in the many countries we visit or work in, whether by observing and participating in situations and events. In the 1990s he was guided by Wolfgang Mommsen in informal postdoctoral work in Germany. This topic of mentoring and the related role of role modeling was reaffirmed when I first did it in mentoring mode. However, much of the literature on mentoring and the programs created for it does not take into account the wide variety that exists, and Research in Education Management & Leadership 5(3), September 2020, 630-638 632 Mentoring is a culture rooted in the society and culture from which it originates. is the configuration. During my time in the Gulf, I realized that formative connections can take on a very different personality due to the influence of Arab cultures, expatriate origins, Islamic principles, and the political climate of the nations that make up the Gulf. My time in the Gulf region has brought up a number of new issues for me, including: Can an expatriate be a mentor or role model for a graduate student in the Gulf? Is it possible to be successful in mentoring and role modeling among the different genders? Can it be done by people of other religions? Can they rise above differences in cultural norms and societal expectations? Is there a universal humanist code of ethics? As a Westerner operating in a Gulf environment, is it possible to get rid of the colonial features of the location? A few of my PhD

students in the UAE have some subsections of short discussion in their dissertations and statistics on these roles, so we can penetrate their ideas to some degree. After that, I did what I often do in situations like this, namely it's important to get in touch with a coworker.

Keywords: Role Model, Educational Administration, Educational Administrators and Role Model, Criteria of Role Modeling in Educational Sciences

Introduction

Components of specialized professional learning include the development of stronger relationship-building abilities, classroom observations, the use of formative data to inform teaching, and the collection and analysis of student evidence (such as work samples and other artifacts) based on educational standards (Güneş, 2012). Sun (2012) argued that the selection of a mentor is an important component of rookie teacher induction programs, and that this process should be handled with care. This is in addition to specialized professional learning, which is also an important component of these programs. When selecting a mentor, Bullough (2012) suggests that the quality of having a strong background as a teacher shouldn't be the only consideration you make. The following are some of the requirements that must be met in order for someone to be considered a mentor: (a) at least three years of successful teaching practice (Sun, 2012, p. 7); (b) one's own teaching; (c) subject matter expertise and subject matter pedagogy; (d) himself and his clients; And (e) compassionate and able to comprehend the requirements of the customers.

Mentoring and role modeling should both be included as part of the in-service training that new teachers receive. Both aspects of social cognitive theory, as outlined by Albert Bandura (Grusec, 1992), and aspects of psychosocial support, as outlined by Allen, Eby, Poteet, and Lima (2004), contribute to the development of role modeling as a field of study. Within the framework of social cognitive theory, peer observations are an example of a role model in which a teacher observes a teaching event and, as a result, models their own behavior after the behaviors observed in the teaching event. On the other hand, psychosocial support consists of role modeling as a means of cultivating and expanding interpersonal connections between a mentor and a client, as well as between a mentor and the mentor's fellow co-workers. Ceballos (2020).

Acculturation, Role Modeling

It is essential to conduct international mentoring and role modeling research through the observation of peers. According to the presentation that Bandura gave, social learning theory, which is also known as social cognitive theory, focuses on the ways in which children's and adults' understanding of social events affects both their behavior and development (Grusec, 1992, page 781). According to Grusec (1992), Bandura's argument regarding the modeling process in social cognitive theory suggested that there are four distinct components that make up the overall process. This was stated in the context of suggesting that there are four unique components that make up the overall process. First, the observer concentrates on the events that are produced or the modeled behavior, and then, using images or verbal means, the observer remembers the observed event or the modeled behavior (Grusec, 1992). Then, it is necessary to attach a value to it in order for the created graphic or verbal representation to be transformed into appropriate behaviors and for the observer to accept the event that was witnessed as a model (Grusec, 1992). In certain circumstances, people may view role modeling in a direct manner, whereas in other circumstances, people may view role modeling in an indirect manner. (Hendry, Bell, & Thomson, 2014; Hunzicker et al., 2017) (Hendry, Bell, & Thomson, 2014) conducted a series of studies that investigated how the process of direct peer observation influences the development of better outcomes for observers. According to the findings of a study conducted by Hendry et al. (2014), participants who observed their peers lecturing reported that the experience either helped them validate their own teaching methods or gave them the opportunity to learn new teaching practices. Hendry et al., 2014 conducted a research study on the topic of direct peer observation of university professors. The findings of the study showed that participants who observed their peers teaching reported that the experience helped them learn new methods of instruction. Hendry et al. (2014) found that respondents also reported other advantageous features of peer observation, such as monitoring student participation in the classroom and a reduced feeling of isolation, as a result of collaborating with colleagues following peer observation. Additionally, respondents reported that peer observation enabled them to monitor the progress of other students in the classroom. It has been demonstrated that interactions with one's peers are the source of both of these benefits. The concept of role modeling can be broken down into its component parts, one of which is indirect role modeling. According to Cruss, Cruess, and Steinhart (2008), individuals engage in indirect role modeling when they observe the actions of their peers, superiors, and other people in their working environment. The majority of the time, people subconsciously process the actions they observe being performed by others.

When it comes to actively evaluating the actions and behaviors exhibited by role models as a component of learning from the witnessed indirect role model, reflection is an essential component that should not be overlooked. Cruess et al. (2008) carried out this research. Following the active observation of role models, Cruises et al. (2008) presented a modeling process framework for clinical practice. This framework encourages clients to investigate their unconscious behaviors, make them conscious, and reflect on their insights regarding these behaviors in order to translate these insights into principles and actions. This was done so that customers could gain knowledge from the behaviors they saw role models exhibiting in front of them in the workplace. Within the framework of the model that has been proposed, clients will actively investigate the "effects and values" of the behaviors that have been observed in order to arrive at "generalization and behavior change" (Cruss et al., 2008, page 719).

Warhurst (2011) provided additional support for the hypothesis that the process of role modeling may be an unconscious process that is not brought to awareness until some kind of reflection takes place. The participants in this research were mid-level managers who learned from senior managers in their work environment on an ad hoc basis rather than through a structural link. The focus of the study was on the ways in which middle managers can learn from top managers. According to Warhurst (2011), participants chose indirect role models based on their perceptions of the competence of the individual they observed in their role as a manager. Because of this, the participants chose to model themselves after indirect examples. On the other hand, the selection of individuals to serve as examples was not restricted to just one person. Participants made their own one-of-a-kind composite role models by selecting relevant characteristics from a variety of role models, which they then selected from among themselves. According to Warhurst (2011), participants omitted a number of characteristics and then combined the remaining characteristics into a composite role model that reflected a mixture of the characteristics. The provision of psychological assistance constitutes the provision of role modeling. When compared to direct and indirect modeling, psychosocial support stands out thanks to its emphasis on the relationships between individuals. "Role modeling, acceptance and validation, counseling and fellowship" are all integral functions of mentoring and are related to a person's level of satisfaction with their mentor (Allen et al., 2004, p. 128).

As a consequence of this, they might be connected to the outcomes of mentorship relationships. According to Ceballos (2020), these functions are connected to an individual's level of contentment with their mentor. Others have arrived at the same conclusions that we have, namely that psychosocial support, also known as professional bonds with counselors and other

individuals, is an important component of the success of rookie teachers (Le Cornu, 2013; Weimer, 2019; Yusko & Feiman-Nemser, 2008). Specifically, these other researchers have found that professional bonds with counselors and other individuals are the most effective form of psychosocial support. For instance, Le Cornu (2013) found that clients who have strong relationships with their classmates at their place of education have a "sense of belonging and social connectedness" (p. 4). Additionally, due to the high quality of the interactions, customers were able to join networks of seasoned trainers and trade ideas with one another, which led to positive results for novice trainers. This reaffirmed the contribution that novice educators make to the school (Le Cornu, 2013). Good interactions were mutual in the sense that clients adopted tactics used by former teachers and that former teachers adopted tactics used by clients. The support that the novice teachers received from their fellow novice teachers was also a factor that contributed to their overall success as educators. According to the questionnaires that were filled out by the teachers, they receive support from their novice teachers in both a professional and personal capacity. This enables them to discuss the challenges and find solutions that are feasible (Le Cornu, 2013). Given the importance of other induction practices in teacher development and retention, principals and other school administrators occupy a crucial place in the mentoring structure and process of a school, as well as in actual role modeling. This is because of the importance of other induction practices.

This is due to the significance of mentoring and other forms of induction practices in the production of new teachers and the maintenance of existing ones. Principals and other school administrators are central to creating a culture of school collaboration where mentoring, role modeling, and other forms of teacher collaboration thrive (Brucknerian & Novotný, 2019; Carver-Thomas & Darling-Hammond, 2017; Correa & Wagner, 2011; Gordon & Lowrey, 2017; Haiyan, Walker, and Xiaowei, 2017; Ingersoll, 2012; Löfström and Eisenschmidt, 2009; Pogodzinski, 2015; Youngs, 2007). On the other hand, similar to mentors, school administrators require professional development Research Educational Administration and Leadership 5(3), September 2020, 640-680 650 in order to create school contexts in which mentoring connections contribute to the growth and retention of teachers. (2017) by Carver-Thomas and Darling-Hammond. According to Gordon and Lowry (2017) and Youngs (2007), school administrators ought to be actively involved in the process of mentoring newly hired teachers in addition to continuing their own education. For instance, the research that was conducted by Correa and Wagner (2011) indicates that it is essential for the success of the mentoring process for school administrators to be involved in the process at an early stage. As a consequence of this, school administrators needed to be actively involved in the program by taking part in activities such as participating in the

orientation of mentees and participating in the process of matching mentors and mentees. In addition to this, the participation of school administrators in the mentoring program has been shown to be beneficial beyond the initial stages of the initiative. Tillman (2005) discovered that a mentee's level of competence increases when a mentor and school management collaborate to guide a mentee through the mentoring process. This helps the mentee become more capable. According to the mentees, the feedback that is created as a result of the collaboration between the mentor and the manager is essential to the mentees' achievement (Correa & Wagner, 2011). It has been demonstrated that on a global scale, it is essential for there to be a culture of schools that encourages the participation of school administrators in mentoring programs for new teachers.

Methodology

According to their findings, mentoring is an essential component in the process of cultivating professional competencies and values. Both of these studies offer a more comprehensive contextual background, with the primary focus being placed on cultural and other socioeconomic factors that may vary. In the study that Benjamin Kutsyuruba, Lorraine Godden, and Keith Walker conducted, titled "The impact of contextual factors on school leaders' early career involvement in teacher counseling: A review of the international research literature," the authors investigate the formal and informal mentoring strategies that are implemented. Beginning a teaching career successfully is critical. Their emphasis on contextual factors within a heuristic framework that influences these practices demonstrates how culture, political systems, social structures and practices, as well as organizational structures, all play a role in the development of these practices.

This study focuses on the significant part that international or foreign teachers play in providing appropriate mentoring and role modeling, as well as the cultural competence that is required of them. They provide their colleagues and students with adequate service, as well as the knowledge and skills that their mentors require to be effective in their roles. In addition to concentrating on how acculturation is conceptualized and carried out as a process, the research also conducts a literature review on the subject by making use of significant databases that cover the span of the previous ten years. The professional development of academics and the careers of academics are the subjects of two separate research studies that focus on mentoring in higher education. Through the use of case study research, Takako Mino's study titled "Corporate Mentoring in West Africa: Comparing Government Regulated and University Managed Models"

(2020) investigates the corporate mentoring programs that are offered in higher education institutions in the West African region.

It focuses on the different kinds of and roles that are inherent in education, education policy, and leadership practices, as well as how these things affect the representation, growth, and aspirations of their respective proteges. According to the findings, certain programs continue to use a coercive approach, which does not fulfill their requirements for mentoring. On the other hand, the findings suggest that successful leadership-based models are those that place a greater emphasis on delegation.

The author compares and contrasts various academic intellectual leadership mentoring programs using a systematic review to investigate the nature and function of academic intellectual leadership mentoring from both a voluntary and institutional perspective. According to the findings, many of the justifications for either can be applied to the other, and doing so can boost productivity for both the mentor and the apprentice. Nevertheless, the findings demonstrate that cultural and political factors have a significant impact, which can be either positive or negative depending on the context.

To gain a better understanding of the requirements placed on international instructors, a literature review covering the years 2009-2019 was carried out. This study was conducted with the intention of determining the degree to which aspects of mentoring, role modeling, and acculturation are reflected in the narratives of international teachers that have been published in journals that have been subjected to peer review. The process of conducting the study led to the discovery and investigation of a previously unrecognized fourth dimension of principles and ITs, which was then further investigated. The results of the literature search led to the identification of four themes that are connected to the three dimensions that were mentioned:

- (a) a requirement for induction;
- (b) role modeling as peer support;
- (c) foreign teacher acculturation concerns; And
- (d) IRs primary perspectives.

Each of these topics was connected to one of the aforementioned three facets in some way. After conducting this type of review of the relevant literature, a number of themes pertaining to international professors and lecturers emerged as a result. These recurring themes have the potential to sway the oversight practices of school administrators, who put in a lot of effort to make sure that international teachers have a positive experience overall.

Techniques for effective supervision can be developed by investigating the practices that have been used by international educators in the areas of counseling, role modeling, and acculturation. Teachers who are natives of countries other than the one in which they are employed are referred to as "foreign teachers." Even though there has been an improvement in the teacher shortage situation since 1999 (Malkus et al., 2015), there are still deficiencies in certain subject areas (for example, mathematics, science, and special education) as well as in 'urban' school settings. Important factors include rurality, high poverty, high minority population, and low achievement" (Aragon, 2016, page 5).

They are referred to by a number of different names in the countries where they are employed as international teachers. These include teachers who were trained overseas and then worked in the United Kingdom (Ministry of Education, 2014), Canada (State of Nova Scotia, t), and the United States (Cultural Vistas, nd), as well as teachers who worked in the United States but were trained internationally. "International teachers" are what the authors of this study refer to as educators who work in a different nation. The specific challenges that international teachers (ITs) face is made more difficult by the necessary cultural adjustments that need to be made in an international education system, each of which has its own culture and traditions (Cross, Hong, & Williams-Johnson, 2011; Dunn, 2011).

Those who work in the field of international training face a variety of obstacles. The importance of needs related to understanding the K-12 culture in which they live, such as student behavior, pedagogy, and school structure, as well as the need for orientation before arriving at the host country and the need for positive peer interactions, has been highlighted by research on international teacher experiences (Cross et al., 2011; Dunn, 2011; Miller, 2018; Datta Roy & Lavery, 2017). This research has highlighted the importance of needs related to understanding the K-12 culture in which they live. These requirements are uncovered through research conducted on teachers all over the world. Further, school administrators emphasized the significance of ongoing professional development in the field of information technology as a means of satisfying

educational and cultural requirements (Dunn, 2011). The difficulties experienced in IT are comparable to those encountered by educators working in different educational systems in other countries. However, in international schools, an emphasis has been placed on reducing teacher turnover through the application of extensive inductive techniques to the international school setting to assist educators in coping with the demands of cultural adaptation (Hayden, 2006). This has been accomplished by applying extensive inductive techniques to the international school setting. Also, in international school settings, principals who are seen as supportive of teachers and who are willing to involve teachers in joint leadership are associated with lower teacher turnover (Mancuso, Roberts, & White, 2010; Odland & Ruzicka, 2009). This is according to research conducted by Mancuso et al. and by Odland and Ruzicka. Research conducted by Mancuso, Roberts, and White (2010) as well as by Odland and Ruzicka (2009) has provided evidence to support this assertion.

Selections from the Literature

Given the similarities that exist between information technology professionals and teachers in international schools, there is an opportunity for ICTs to transition into a new role through the implementation of strategies that are linked to new teacher induction and effective teacher development (Ceballos, 2020).

Mentoring and role modeling are practices that have been linked to improved teaching methods as well as student achievement (Darling-Hammond, Wei, Andree, Richardson, & Orphanos, 2009; Ingersoll & Strong, 2011; Krasnoff, 2014; New Teacher Center, 2015). These practices are particularly important. In particular, practices involving mentoring and role modeling have been linked to improvements in teaching practices as well as increased levels of academic achievement among students.

according to the New Teacher Center (2015), principals and other school administrators play an extremely important part in the growth of information technology (IT). This is due to the fact that they establish the conditions for productive teacher development, effective teacher collaboration, and outstanding induction and mentoring. However, the most important thing that school administrators should do is read published works that contain the experiences of IT professionals in order to get a better understanding of the requirements of IT.

In the end, the objective of this review of the relevant literature was to zero in on a single research question: to what extent does the body of international teacher literature that focuses on IT fables represent the requirements for mentoring, role modeling, and acculturation? A discussion of mentoring, role modeling, acculturation, cultural intelligence, and business outcomes are included in the conceptual framework. This discussion is based on research conducted on prospective first-year teachers, in addition to studies on cross-cultural psychology and management. The objective of this discussion is to incorporate this work into the framework that is currently in place for research. (Bullough, 2012; Capizzi, Wehby, & Sandmel, 2010; Carver-Thomas & Darling-Hammond, 2017; Correa & Wagner, 2011; Darling-Hammond et al., 2009; Gordon & et al., 2009) Studies have shown that mentoring is an essential component for the success of novice teachers in the classroom. Lowrey, 2017; Kessels, 2010; Lofstrom & Eisenschmidt, 2009; Sun, 2012; Tillman, 2005).

Carver-Thomas and Darling-Hammond (2017), Gordon and Research in Education Management & Leadership 5(3), September 2020, 640-680 644 Mentoring strategies by Carver-Thomas and Darling-Hammond (2017) According to Lowrey (2017), the continued employment of first-year teachers in schools is an important factor. First, Carver-Thomas and Darling-Hammond (2017) presented a set of recommendations aimed at assisting inexperienced educators. The following components are included with these instructions:

- (a) the appointment of a mentor;*
- (b) frequent meetings with the appointed mentor;*
- (c) focus on observation and feedback in the classroom;*
- (d) analysis of student data to identify areas of improvement and strengths;*
- (e) discussion of teaching topics; And*
- (f) it is important to work together to develop a professional growth plan (p. 34).*

In addition, Gordon and Lowrey (2017) argued that although formal mentoring is an important component of the mentoring structure, mentoring should be understood as a web rather than a structure. This is despite the fact that formal mentoring is an important part of the mentoring structure. According to Gordon and Lowrey (2017), the mentoring network that contributes to the growth of rookie teachers consists of administrators, mentors (both formal and informal), college and university professors, school support staff, students, parents, and inductions. This network also contributes to the growth of veteran teachers. In addition, novice educators should be encouraged

to seek informal mentors due to the additional contributions provided by informal mentors outside of the standard mentoring model (Gordon & Lowrey, 2017; Correa & Wagner, 2011). This is because informal mentors provide these contributions in addition to the standard mentoring model. This is due to the fact that informal mentors offer additional contributions that go beyond the scope of the traditional mentoring paradigm. A number of studies, including Capizzi et al. (2010), Lofstrom and Eisenschmidt (2009), and Correa and Wagner (2011), have investigated the role that mentoring plays in effective teaching practices and the progression of professional careers. Researchers found that pre-service teachers' instructional proficiency increased after receiving feedback in a recorded session, according to the findings of a study that was conducted by Capizzi et al. (2010) involving pre-service teachers. The study was conducted with the participation of pre-service teachers. Pre-service teachers who took part in the instructional feedback process found out that it was beneficial to follow the lessons with their mentors. This was one of the things they learned. Researchers in Estonia found that beginning teachers were given assistance in the form of mentoring by Ceballos (2020). This assistance included the development of both personal and professional knowledge, as well as feedback, peer support, and reciprocity. This was found out through a survey that was given to novice teachers about their experiences with mentoring.

According to Lofstrom and Eisenschmidt (2009), the aspects of a mentoring relationship that are most crucial to its success are trust, access to the mentor, and the mentoring relationship itself. However, participants highlighted the need for mentors to support rather than directly direct reflection; the need for mentors to participate in professional development in order to assist the mentor-client relationship; and the need to integrate mentoring into the culture of schools. As a consequence of this, Correa and Wagner (2011) came to the realization that informal mentors are indispensable to the mentoring process. This is due to the fact that informal mentors offer rookie trainers valuable feedback on their teaching.

Argument

It is essential to the success of mentoring relationships that one be able to participate in mentoring activities that contribute to the development of the mentor. A number of studies (Bullough, 2012; Darling-Hammond et al., 2009; Kessels & Kessels, 2010; Sun, 2012) came to the conclusion that mentors need to make and maintain adequate preparation before taking on a role as a mentor.

As a result of the specialized knowledge and skills that mentors need, this expansion is essential to the outcomes of mentor-mentee relationships. Mentors and mentees both benefit from this growth. For instance, mentors experience dissonance as a result of the conflicting goals of providing peer support to clients, offering support to novice teachers, and providing critical feedback in order to improve the outcomes for students (Bullough, 2012). This causes mentors to feel pressured and stressed out. Because of this, mentors often have mixed feelings about the most effective ways to guide newbie trainers. In addition, beginning educators have expressed the opinion that mentors should be dependable, helpful, and offer a "level of difficulty" to the client in order to improve teaching practice (Kessels, 2010, page 33). In addition, mentors should educate their clients about teaching and learning, provide clients with feedback and formative assessment, and support clients as they navigate new experiences and challenges (Sun, 2012). In addition, as a result of the one-of-a-kind role that they play, mentors are frequently viewed as instruments for the retention and development of teachers, as well as the driving force behind changes in the culture of schools (Bullough, 2012). Because of these requirements, there is a pressing need for educators to participate in specialized professional development in order for them to become effective mentors (Kessels, 2010) and improve the outcomes for their students (Darling-Hammond et al., 2009).

Components of specialized professional learning include the development of stronger relationship-building abilities, classroom observations, the use of formative data to inform teaching, and the collection and analysis of student evidence (such as work samples and other artifacts) based on educational standards (Güneş, 2012). Sun (2012) argued that the selection of a mentor is an important component of rookie teacher induction programs, and that this process should be handled with care. This is in addition to specialized professional learning, which is also an important component of these programs. When selecting a mentor, Bullough (2012) suggests that the quality of having a strong background as a teacher shouldn't be the only consideration you make. The following are some of the requirements that must be satisfied by mentors:

- (a) three years or more of effective teaching practice (Sun, 2012, p. 7);*
- (b) one's own teaching;*
- (c) content knowledge and content pedagogy;*
- (d) himself and his clients; And*
- (e) empathetic and understand clients' needs.*

Mentoring and role modeling should both be included as part of the in-service training that new teachers receive. Both aspects of social cognitive theory, as outlined by Albert Bandura (Grusec, 1992), and aspects of psychosocial support, as outlined by Allen, Eby, Poteet, and Lima (2004), contribute to the development of role modeling as a field of study. Within the framework of social cognitive theory, peer observations are an example of a role model in which a teacher observes a teaching event and, as a result, models their own behavior after the behaviors observed in the teaching event. On the other hand, psychosocial support consists of role modeling as a means of cultivating and expanding interpersonal connections between a mentor and a client, as well as between a mentor and the mentor's fellow co-workers, Ceballos (2020).

Acculturation, Role Modeling

It is essential to conduct international mentoring and role modeling research through the observation of peers. According to the presentation that Bandura gave, social learning theory, which is also known as social cognitive theory, focuses on the ways in which children's and adults' understanding of social events affects both their behavior and development (Grusec, 1992, page 781). According to Grusec (1992), Bandura's argument regarding the modeling process in social cognitive theory suggested that there are four distinct components that make up the overall process. This was stated in the context of suggesting that there are four unique components that make up the overall process. First, the observer concentrates on the events that are produced or the modeled behavior, and then, using images or verbal means, the observer remembers the observed event or the modeled behavior (Grusec, 1992). Then, it is necessary to attach a value to it in order for the created graphic or verbal representation to be transformed into appropriate behaviors and for the observer to accept the event that was witnessed as a model (Grusec, 1992). In certain circumstances, people may view role modeling in a direct manner, whereas in other circumstances, people may view role modeling in an indirect manner. (Hendry, Bell, & Thomson, 2014; Hunzicker et al., 2017) (Hendry, Bell, & Thomson, 2014) conducted a series of studies that investigated how the process of direct peer observation influences the development of better outcomes for observers. According to the findings of a study conducted by Hendry et al. (2014), participants who observed their peers lecturing reported that the experience either helped them validate their own teaching methods or gave them the opportunity to learn new teaching practices. Hendry et al., 2014 conducted a research study on the topic of direct peer observation of university professors. The findings of the study showed that participants who observed their peers teaching reported that the experience helped them learn new methods of instruction. Hendry et al. (2014) found that

respondents also reported other advantageous features of peer observation, such as monitoring student participation in the classroom and a reduced feeling of isolation, as a result of collaborating with colleagues following peer observation. Additionally, respondents reported that peer observation enabled them to monitor the progress of other students in the classroom. It has been demonstrated that interactions with one's peers are the source of both of these benefits. The concept of role modeling can be broken down into its component parts, one of which is indirect role modeling. According to Cruss, Cruess, and Steinhart (2008), individuals engage in indirect role modeling when they observe the actions of their peers, superiors, and other people in their working environment. The majority of the time, people subconsciously process the actions they observe being performed by others.

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Warhurst (2011) provided additional support for the hypothesis that the process of role modeling may be an unconscious process that is not brought to awareness until some kind of reflection takes place. The participants in this research were mid-level managers who learned from senior managers in their work environment on an ad hoc basis rather than through a structural link. The purpose of the study was to investigate the manner in which middle managers gain knowledge from top managers. Participants chose indirect role models based on their assessments of the observed individual's capabilities as a manager (Warhurst, 2011). Because of this, the participants chose to model themselves after indirect examples. On the other hand, the selection of individuals to serve as examples was not restricted to just one person. Participants made their own one-of-a-kind composite role models by selecting relevant characteristics from a variety of role models, which they then selected from among themselves. According to Warhurst (2011), participants omitted a number of characteristics and then combined the remaining characteristics into a

composite role model that reflected a mixture of the characteristics. The provision of psychological assistance constitutes the provision of role modeling. When compared to direct and indirect modeling, psychosocial support stands out thanks to its emphasis on the relationships between individuals. "Role modeling, acceptance and validation, counseling and fellowship" are all integral functions of mentoring and are related to a person's level of satisfaction with their mentor (Allen et al., 2004, p. 128).

As a consequence of this, they might be connected to the outcomes of mentorship relationships. According to Ceballos (2020), these functions are connected to an individual's level of contentment with their mentor. Others have arrived at the same conclusions that we have, namely that psychosocial support, also known as professional bonds with counselors and other individuals, is an important component of the success of rookie teachers (Le Cornu, 2013; Weimer, 2019; Yusko & Feiman-Nemser, 2008). Specifically, these other researchers have found that professional bonds with counselors and other individuals are the most effective form of psychosocial support. For instance, Le Cornu (2013) found that clients who have strong relationships with their classmates at their place of education have a "sense of belonging and social connectedness" (p. 4). Additionally, due to the high quality of the interactions, customers were able to join networks of seasoned trainers and trade ideas with one another, which led to positive results for novice trainers. This reaffirmed the contribution that novice educators make to the school (Le Cornu, 2013). Good interactions were mutual in the sense that clients adopted tactics used by former teachers and that former teachers adopted tactics used by clients. The support that the novice teachers received from their fellow novice teachers was also a factor that contributed to their overall success as educators. According to the questionnaires that were filled out by the teachers, they receive support from their novice teachers in both a professional and personal capacity. This enables them to discuss the challenges and find solutions that are feasible (Le Cornu, 2013). Given the importance of other induction practices in teacher development and retention, principals and other school administrators occupy a crucial place in the mentoring structure and process of a school, as well as in actual role modeling. This is because of the importance of other induction practices.

This is due to the significance of mentoring and other forms of induction practices in the production of new teachers and the maintenance of existing ones. Principals and other school administrators are central to creating a culture of school collaboration where mentoring, role modeling, and other forms of teacher collaboration thrive (Brucknerian & Novotný, 2019; Carver-Thomas & Darling-Hammond, 2017; Correa & Wagner, 2011; Gordon & Lowrey, 2017; Haiyan,

Walker, and Xiaowei, 2017; Ingersoll, 2012; Lfstrm and Eisenschmidt, 2009; Pogodzinski, 2015; Youngs, 2007). On the other hand, similar to mentors, school administrators require professional development Research Educational Administration and Leadership 5(3), September 2020, 640-680 650 in order to create school contexts in which mentoring connections contribute to the growth and retention of teachers. (2017) by Carver-Thomas and Darling-Hammond. According to Gordon and Lowry (2017) and Youngs (2007), school administrators ought to be actively involved in the process of mentoring newly hired teachers in addition to continuing their own education. For instance, the research that was conducted by Correa and Wagner (2011) indicates that it is essential for the success of the mentoring process for school administrators to be involved in the process at an early stage. As a consequence of this, school administrators needed to be actively involved in the program by taking part in activities such as participating in the orientation of mentees and participating in the process of matching mentors and mentees. In addition to this, the participation of school administrators in the mentoring program has been shown to be beneficial beyond the initial stages of the initiative. Tillman (2005) discovered that a mentee's level of competence increases when a mentor and school management collaborate to guide a mentee through the mentoring process. This helps the mentee become more capable. According to the mentees, the feedback that is created as a result of the collaboration between the mentor and the manager is essential to the mentees' achievement (Correa & Wagner, 2011). It has been demonstrated that on a global scale, it is essential for there to be a culture of schools that encourages the participation of school administrators in mentoring programs for new teachers.

Conclusion

Mentoring and role modeling should be included as part of the in-service training that new teachers receive. These practices are influenced by aspects of social cognitive theory and psychosocial support. In the context of social cognitive theory, peer observations are a type of role model in which a teacher observes a teaching event and adopts behaviors from the teaching event. These behaviors are then shared with the students. In the context of psychosocial support, role modeling is a strategy for fostering the growth and expansion of interpersonal connections between a mentor and a client, as well as between a mentor and the client's other coworkers.

It has been shown that validating teaching methods through direct peer observation enables new teaching practices to be implemented. According to a number of studies, peer observation can result in the development of novel instructional strategies as well as a reduction in feelings of

social isolation. The participants observe the actions of their peers, superiors, and other people in their working environment, and they process the behaviors they see in a subconscious manner. This type of role modeling is known as indirect role modeling. When it comes to actively evaluating the actions and behaviors exhibited by role models as a component of learning from the witnessed indirect role model, reflection is an essential component that should not be overlooked. The development of strong psychosocial support networks, which can also be referred to as professional bonds with various other people, is an essential component for the success of first-year educators. Clients who feel a sense of belonging and social connectedness in their lives have strong relationships with their classmates and colleagues at school. Because of the quality of the interactions, customers were able to join networks of seasoned trainers and share their thoughts with one another, which led to favorable results for inexperienced trainers.

One of the factors that contributed to the success of novice educators was the support they received from other novice educators in their field. In addition to serving as actual role models, principals and other school administrators play an essential part in the structure and process of mentoring at their respective schools. The practices of mentoring and induction are extremely important for the growth and retention of teachers. Mentoring, role modeling, and various other forms of teacher collaboration can only succeed in an environment where principals and other school administrators play a pivotal role in the formation of a culture of collaboration. Professional development is necessary for school administrators in order to establish school environments in which mentoring connections contribute to the growth and retention of teachers. It is essential for teachers to maintain their own education and actively participate in the mentoring of new teachers. According to the findings of research, it is essential for the success of the mentoring program for school administrators to be involved in the process at an early stage. As a result of the correlation between increased mentee competence and feedback and increased collaboration between mentors and school management, it is imperative that school administrators be involved in the process of assisting novice educators on a global scale.

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